

The Phenomenon Of Boyat: Theoretical Milestones For Sociological Reading

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 24, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: March 19, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Social Security, Boyat, Gender, Homosexuality, Other Gender Behavior</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4623316</p>	<p><i>The current study aims to highlight the phenomenon of "Boyat" (The Mannish Women) from a sociological perspective - sociology - as a threat to social security in Arab societies. There is no doubt that one of the mechanisms for achieving social security is the ability to address the phenomena that deviate from social traditions, values and standards of the dominant system in society. The study was divided into three axes. The first axis discussed : reading in the concept of social security, and the second axis discussed : the phenomenon of Boyat : its concept, manifestations and social consequences. The study also discussed in the third axis: Sociological approaches to the phenomenon of Boyat . The study found that Arab societies need to study the phenomenon of Boyat, the social recognition of its seriousness, directing the empirical research to the social and cultural factors surrounding deviant sexual practices, and including the field of gender study as a main research in sociology.</i></p>

Introduction

Social security is a primary necessity for the stability of human groups. Its importance stems from the fact that it has been at the root of life since creation, without which societies cannot continue and settle their systems. It is necessary to have viable governments, institutions, and citizens that can innovate in their own fields, leading to prosperity in society. It may explain the increased attention to social security since the 1990s; the beginning of the technology and information revolution and the transformation into the so-called knowledge society. Indeed, the progress of societies is measured by their ability to embrace innovation and transform it into ideas that can be applied. This can be achieved only in a secure society. Since social security is not limited to one class or specific race, it is the responsibility of all the actors in society to maintain it. The importance of social security and the necessity of committing to it is emphasized in international charters and national constitutions, for example, article 22 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights states that everyone as a member of society has the right of social security. This is to be achieved through national efforts and international cooperation in accordance with the systems and economic, social and educational resources of each country, which are indispensable for human dignity and for the free development of his personality. Societies may be affected by changes which threatens their social security. One of the most dangerous and hidden phenomena under fear of stigmatization of the family or society, is probably the phenomenon of "Boyat", and if the overwhelming majority of people in all societies are homosexual people. However, homosexuality - and Boyat are one of their manifestations and the common terms used in Gulf societies - is a phenomenon that exists in all cultures. They represent minorities and segments of human beings whose tastes and sexual preferences differ from the dominant general pattern (Geddins, 2001).

Boyat is spread in a number of Arab societies with closed environments on one type only; many girls or women, such as schools and universities, meet from all social sectors. It is subject to variations both in the extent of its occurrence and in the way in which society and culture perceive them (Smith, 1998). Taking such behavior as the basis of a social identity - even an organized identity and a life course - is a threat to the social security of Arab societies, which the current research will seek to clarify.

Research Problem:

There are recent phenomena that threaten the security of societies, from which not even welfare societies are spared, which may stigmatize them and transform them into fragile societies vulnerable to unrest, so all social phenomena that threaten social security are often repressed. "Boyat" is probably one of the negative phenomena and unacceptable practices that have plagued societies with social imbalances, especially in the light of social and economic changes in societies, and the resulting bad practices that pose a threat to the security of society. The problem of the study is identifying the phenomenon of Boyat as a threat to social security, whether on the structure of the Arab family or society as a whole, from a sociological perspective.

Study Objective and Questions:

In light of the above, the current study aims to identify the dimensions of the phenomenon of Boyat and its consequences and the extent of its threat to social security, by answering the most important questions:

1-What does the concept of social security mean?

2- Who are "Boyat"?

3- How do you explain the phenomenon of Boyat in sociology – Sociological - ?

To answer the above questions, the study will be divided into several axes for each axis to be allocated to answer a question; the focus of the study will be as follows: The first axis is the concept of social security: Nature of the Concept.

The second axis is the phenomenon of Boyat: Its concept, manifestations and social consequences. The third axis is sociological approaches to the phenomenon of Boyat.

The Importance of the Study:

Studies in the field of confronting abnormalities are few, therefore this study marks the path and encourages other researchers to make further studies. It is also a scientific addition to studies on gender and social security in sociology.

As for the practical aspect, this study is descriptive and uses the reanalysis and dismantling of a number of articles and sites on the Internet and studies of the effects of social and cultural change in societies and their reinstallation. Society has shifted from its traditional to modern state, affecting the community value system and this requires looking at mechanisms to counter the negative consequences of this, with a view to reaching a number of measures that would establish the right values for social security. These are listed below in the mentioned order.

The first is social security: Reading the concept:

At first it should be noted that social security is an old concept that man has known since the early beginning of living in groups. This concept has been reintroduced in modern times. It is defined as the product of partnership in bearing the responsibility for security among all members of society and various country systems; It includes community police, community justice and community public order (Albashree, 2009).

Social security definitions have been numerous. Their uses and significance have varied, and even opinions may be said to have conflicted on what it means. This can be explained by the multiplicity of security types in general; the need for security varies with different periods of time. The same threats are different from times to times, as well as social security or community security, human security, national security or domestic security, public security, collective security, common security, regional security and group security, for sectarian groups or nations, even if they do not take the form of a state, this means preserving "identity". As problems affecting human safety and property have worsened, specialized security clauses have emerged; such as industrial security, food security, cultural security, environmental security, etc. (Albashree, 2009). Governments can play the role of protecting their citizens and creating a just society through civil society organizations. (Moqbil, 2012).

One definition of social security is the one presented by the United Nations in the Human Development Report: "the security of the regions from external aggression or the protection of national interests in external agreements or global protection against nuclear threats" (Human Development Report, 1994). It is clear that this definition focuses on national security from military threats, a concept that has evolved - much later, defined by the same organization. According to the Arab Human Development Report 2009, "social security enables peoples to contain or avoid threats to their lives, livelihoods and dignity" (Arab Human Development Report, 2009). It is clear that the second definition focuses on the reassurance of individuals and societies over their physical lives in different aspects, and on their moral lives, especially human dignity. The report itself identified it in the following year (2010) as: "Getting rid of fear and want," living safely from chronic risks such as hunger, disease, and repression, and protecting against emergency and harmful accidents that disrupt daily lifestyles, whether at home, at work, or in society" (Arab Human Development Report, 2010). Thus, the first definition, formulated 20 years ago, expressed military security, i.e., it is limited to the protection of the State's borders, against any aggression on its territory. It is an old model of security, whereas the new model the emphasis has shifted from land to people living on this land. The second definition focuses on the national security of peoples and communities, and the third is on the physical and moral security of individuals and communities in the preventive form - protection from - and therapy of - disposal of... -. It is also noted when comparing the first definition with the third definition; a radical shift from thinking about peace and conflict prevention to protecting against all threats to societies, which means living in safety from chronic risks, such as poverty, hunger and repression, and protection from harmful emergencies that disrupt daily lifestyles, whether caused by violence, earthquakes, or financial crises. This broad concept of security is thus contradicted with the narrow old concept of military and humanitarian personnel.

Security has to take into consideration various threats to human security, dignity and livelihood resources, in addition to all threats to societies, including violence, poverty causing violence and threats of violence

contribute to the spread of poverty. This concept also addresses the balance between investment in military abilities and investment in human life, living resources and dignity. It focuses on providing minimum capabilities and protecting them from severe dangers. Over time, this concept of human security has become a central element in many global initiatives and has been adopted by governments. It has been incorporated into their public programs and policies by regional and international organizations. The concept of security continues to have an increasingly influential impact in the global context. Western literature uses the term "Human Security" to signify "the absence and loss of fear and threats at the state and individual levels, that is; a person is free of fear, freedom from fear; and from harm or physical, sexual and psychological abuse, violence and persecution. He should be free from need, as well. It also refers to disaster management, whether caused by war or natural disasters such as hurricanes, famines or human-induced disasters, as crisis management" (Kaldor, 2011). Some scholars define it as an expansion of the idea of "protecting" individuals from risk and providing physical and psychological protection, so that a sense of human dignity and welfare prevail (Tadjbakhsh & Chenoy, 2007). The term "social security" is used to refer to welfare programs, and income maintenance and social security programs that provide protection against emergency social conditions; including poverty, disability, handicap, unemployment, etc. This definition reflects the scarcity of the term usage to refer to security in the overall sense. It is not linked to basic necessities such as food, clothing, shelter, education, money and health care. This latter meaning, social security, is used in both the American Encyclopedia of Sociology and the Encyclopedia Britannica.

It refers to "the measures established by government legislations to preserve individual or family income or to provide income when some or all sources of income are disrupted or exceptionally highly expensive, such as raising children, or paying for health care. Thus, the benefits of cash social security may be provided to people who face illness, disability, unemployment, crop failure, loss of marital partners, maternity, responsibility for the care of young children, or retirement from work. Social security benefits can be acquired in cash or in kind when medical and rehabilitation are needed and local assistance is available. (www. Britannica.com). It is clear from the above that social security may take an institutional form to provide income for the individual in cases of disability, unemployment and disasters through social security institutions, called "social security", and may take the form of protection against the military threat, called "national or military security". It could come in a general sense of protecting against fear, want, and need.

Thus social security can be defined in this paper as: "To protect against risks and social groups by all means that contribute to society, and in the interest of following the community's traditions in terms of belonging to them, for the sake of stability and well-being in society for "individuals".

The study of social security has increased since the 1990s; as the technology, information and transformation revolution began, societies have advanced as measured by their ability to embrace innovation and transform it into ideas that can be applied. This can only be achieved in a secure society. In this regard, globalization and the shrinking border between societies, the revolution of technological inventions and the end of cold war ad bilateral sides cannot be overlooked, which did not reduce insecurity, but rather left uncertainty.

Moreover, free-economy policies have widened the gap between the haves and have-nots, making many excluded, marginalized, feel isolated and alienated in their societies, especially as the sense of responsibility and the ability of states to change their societies on the one hand, and the fragmentation and separation between members of society on the other, based on ethnicity or religious extremism (Tadjbakhsh & Chenoy, 2007) has diminished. It may be also a result that society is not governed by a doctrine or by a law as a reference to its members, which makes it vulnerable to chaos, lack of moral components, and reduces self-restraint, and then is unjust or flawed, which is considered to be a threat to the destruction of society; Therefore, lack of social security occurs when chaos and apathy are widespread, corruption and delinquency are widespread, robberies, killings, violence, terrorist acts and hateful sectarian acts - sedition - are increasing, and new cases emerge in society, such as the abduction of girls and boys, and the flight of girls for months and to alternative family sites. The increase in the number of assaults inside the walls of homes and in open areas and the delay in criminal acts to the extent that they are portrayed. Drugs and their users among the two genders, suicide, homosexuality and its many forms, including "Boyat" spread.

In the light of the foregoing, social security is essential to the achievement of the living and economic sufficiency and the life stability of a citizen, who feels that he has firm foundations in his society to preserve his / her existence, being and belonging to a homeland. Stability in life of the individual is essential to maintaining his / her emotional and psychological balance. It is imperative in all societies, for all individuals and for citizens, it also leads to the stability of societies, which is the foundation upon which all actors in society are based toward creativity and innovation, leading societies to progress, development and well-being.

Meanwhile, the mechanisms for achieving social security, as dealt by Mustafa Al-Ougi and Mansour Al-Qarni, are based on the cohesion of the members of society, and the ability to deal with difficulties and scourges through the system of customs and traditions in which society believes. The stability factors based on understanding, coexistence, the spirit of citizenship, a sense of belonging and a desire to express positive

participation in the service of the group for self-realization, on the one hand, and to gain satisfaction and acceptance from the group on the other hand. The availability of a fair and competent judicial system, the penal institutions, and good authority, tolerance toward the delinquent, and social institutions and charities. The deepness of religious faith, social justice and social solidarity, family upbringing, educational institutions, loyalty and patriotism, ethical values, social norms, and the media (Ougi, 1983) are also important to maintain social security. In general, threats to social security must be identified in order to treat symptoms and protect or prevent the recurrence of such threats (Tadjbakhsh & Chenoy, 2007). In the case of mechanisms for social security, it should be noted that there is a mistaken belief that the terms "security keeping" and "security making" are the same. In fact, we have to differentiate between them. The first term is that maintaining security is an attempt to preserve a reality that may be unjust. Therefore, any attempt to modify that reality is an attempt to destabilize security and therefore an attempt that must be stopped. So everyone who is in an excellent position will try to maintain security. This may be to preserve security at the expense of the rights of others. The other term, on the other hand, security making includes the idea of making and not preserving security. This means achieving objective conditions for ensuring security. The police do not make security but maintain security. The family makes security by preserving and inculcating social and cultural customs and traditions in its children, and school, the economy by eliminating unemployment. These are measures to make security, so that we do not create a thief, we should solve the unemployment problem.

To avoid creating homosexuals, social-upbringing institutions must inculcate values and ethics. These measures are called security-making. (www.swms.net) The phenomenon of Boyat requires both former concepts, from maintaining security in two ways through security protection – police – and continuous monitoring within educational institutions; and prior to that point, making security by social upbringing through their different institutions to gain customs and values that protect against deviation.

It is clear from the above that social security is a requirement, necessity, and community reality that individuals and societies seek to achieve and learn what it is likely to threaten it, so we will learn about one phenomenon with negative consequences for social security in more detail in the next axis.

The Second Axis, the Phenomenon of Boyat: Its Concept, Manifestations and Social Consequences:

Boyat is a term that means feminization of the English word Boy, which means a boy, and adding A and T to the end of the word, meaning "The Mannish Women", who are similar to men's appearance and behavior, or what is called "fourth sex". It is a reflection of feminine rebel against God-made perfect nature of a girl. It is a word that refers to a girl who has male traits despite her female identity and shown by her actions and dealings with others, or that she tries everything she can to be different from her own reality; to convince who are around her that she is not a female. They may give themselves male names, dress like men, walk like men, deepen their voices, and cut their hair like men. While some go to the extent of growing hair in the moustache area with the men's razor blade to make the hair look more apparent, and may include some suspicious relationships with other girls, and even to the extent of forbidden relationships with other girls (Alkhelyawy).

A number of factors are contributing to the spread of the phenomenon of Boyat (Salahuddin and Alkhelyawy): including family factors, psychological factors, social factors, and physiological factors. Family factors are manifested in the lack of proper education and the family's losing its guiding role - as a result of family disintegration or the absence of parental control and being busy not to follow up children or relying on foreign nannies, the dysfunction of upbringing techniques may create such behavior in girls; the upbringing of girls among male brothers and leaving them without guidance or permanent playing with boys of their own small age may make them take boys' behaviors, and the uncertainty of girls' relations with each other; It may leave room for relationships that may be promiscuous. Parents who differentiate between males and females, giving the most attention to males, while females are oppressed and discriminated against in treatment compared to their male brothers to the point of beating them. All this may make the girl an imperfect female and willing to be of the other superior gender from her parents' point of view.

The psychological factors are manifested in sexuality disorder, due to the girl being raped or harassed (Sexual Harassment) which causes hatred against her own gender. The girl's personality may be fragile, so she seeks to play the role of a man to get rid of that weakness with strong qualities and ability to endure and patience.

This abnormality may seem to be caused by organic causes, but in fact this explanation is not possible; in most cases, it is mentioned (Bandle, 1979) that doctors like Andra Artus asserted that "in the vast majority of cases, homosexuality is not a result of an abnormality of the glands, it is a special behavior due to psychological factors". Organic preparations may pave the way for this abnormality, but in most cases the underlying cause remains psychological; in humans, organic sex is not enough to determine the psychological sex; in the same vein, male may very deeply refuse to accept his status as a male, and female rejection to her femininity may also occur at the early stages of life.

Social factors are evident: In the confusion of a girl's self-identity and her self-perception of what she believes to be important in her life, which some social scientists tend to talk about the role of socialization, which starts from individualism and a sense of freedom. During this process, an individual grows in a sense of identity and a degree of independence in thought and action. Sexuality; sexual orientation is one of the most important sources

in the formation of identity (Geddins, 2001). A gender-oriented homosexual person does not go in the quest for the other end; he looks for a self-image; that is, looking for a mirror in which it reflects more of its own image than looking for a complement (Bandlely, 1979).

Who is likely to be subjected to it, the spirit of rebellion because of the strict restrictions of society on it, especially in our Arab male societies, which negatively affects our daughters who find that they have no place to get their social status except by being similar to men, and some still deal with women as being second degree of humans in the absence of a good example. The lack of community recognition of the phenomenon, the imbalance of value systems and the prevalence of consumption patterns, and the lust for the satisfaction of desires and benefits, friendships, the stranding of our educational curricula through the spread of international schools, attempts to erase Islamic and Arab identity and attempts to instill Western values instead. The fascination, which generates a sense of psychological defeat against the West's material civilization.

Emotional : Many girls feel deprived of love and sentiment, the girl who looks for love that is not found from a guy .The Social conditions in moving from the same-gender inclination to the opposite gender.

The inclination to have the same gender quickly goes away to allow the attraction to the other gender; the desire to have a connection, and living conditions play a significant role in this development, to a large extent determine the speed and amount of how adolescent passes this stage .If adolescents have only interactions with the same gender, such as in boarding schools and gender-segregated communities, it is difficult for adolescents to go beyond the same gender stage; this is where gender socialization seems important, provided that socialization is conscious; to help adolescents transcend childhood sexuality and homosexuality, which is an extension of childhood sexuality to heterosexual sex, and to have a mature tendency to the opposite gender. It is worth noting that this socialization helps adolescents move toward the discovery of the other; this basic discovery, to the complete character of humanity out of its shell. Thus, the completion of love that does not occur unless one transcends one's own self to another being. For the boy, females are the other ones who differ from him, and males are only the same.

The tendency to the same gender quickly goes away to allow the attraction to the other gender, the desire to communicate with him. The conditions of life play a significant role in this development. They determine the speed and amount of how adolescent passes the stage of the same gender to a great extent. In addition, if adolescents have only interactions with the same gender, as in the internal schools or communities that are firmly gender-segregated, it is difficult for adolescents to go beyond the same gender stage .This is where gender socialization seems important, provided that socialization is conscious; to help adolescents transcend childhood sexuality and homosexuality, which is an extension of childhood sexuality; to heterosexual sex, and to mature tendency to the opposite gender. It is worth noting that this intermingling helps adolescents move toward the discovery of another, this basic discovery, to the complete character of humanity by coming out of its shell, thus the complete love that does not take place unless one transcends one's own self to another being. For the boy, the girl is the other who is different from him, and the male is only the same."

Morally: Lack of good role models, sound of advice and guidance, blind tradition and simulation.

Religious : Straying away from religion , the disorientation of official religious institutions from their roles of spreading values. The Islamic movements in some countries are limited in return for the spread of the westernized and pornographic movements.

Organic or Physiological : lacking beauty in girl , dysfunctions of hormones, the presence of mixed organs ,the imbalance of the percentage of testosterone and estrogen where the first is more than the latter, despite having all the feminine looks of organs. The first Gulf War led some researchers to accuse American forces of using biological materials .

Contemporary Means of Communication: The media, the internet, and satellite channels; especially European channels. European societies deal with such phenomena in terms of personal freedom, girls watching violent films, and such , the existence of series that tackle that case and the calls of woman's freedom without moral control.

From the foregoing the phenomenon of Boyat is a perverse behavior, resulting from the interaction of a range of interlocking factors that are mutually reliable, so it is not at the level of reality that we live, but we have not yet had to draw dividing lines between these dimensions with a view to studying and reflecting on the different societies and individuals (Alkhelyawy).

There are three stages which girls transform into a Boyat:

The first stage is only the appearance of girls, known as transvestism, which means wanting to wear the other gender clothing and taking on the role they play (Bullough, 1974). With the increased feeling like a boy , she turns into the second stage , which is the most serious, whereas her behaviours carries her beliefs .She acts as boys' behaviours of the general appearance, the formation of gangs, and the imposition of irregular relations with some female students, which sometimes take the form of harassment in school baths and their forms of physical contact and kissing. The third stage takes these girls with all their meanings of becoming homosexuals, and the

girl becomes in a sick stage that needs psychological treatment and social rehabilitation. As for how relations with other Boyat are formed; the relationship between “Boyat” and her friend is at the outset a form of mutual admiration, which quickly develops into a psychologically, physically, and mentally dangerous homosexual relationship, in which a “Boyat” girl seeks to identify her “Boyat” counterparts, in order to form groups that practice certain sports together; Like football or volleyball. They also take the behavior of young men of harassing and flirting with girls, and there may even be harassment in private places ; Like female students dorms, girls' schools and colleges, or women's parks. They enter into emotional relationships with girls that may reach the stage of homosexuality, which can pose a real danger to girls in places of assembly (Salahuddin).

If homosexuality is present worldwide, the phenomenon of Boyat is concentrated in closed environments on a single type, where many girls or women meet, such as schools, universities, or institutions from all social sectors, including the rich and the middle class. They are the ones who live lost, who live in family disorientation, who challenge the behavior of family power and are subject to enormous variations, whether in the extent of its occurrence or in the way in which society and culture perceive homosexual practices and relationships (Smith 1998); Taking such behavior as the basis for a social identity - indeed, as an organized identity and a life course - is a modern phenomenon, and the forms of homosexual identity, their arrangements and their lifestyles reveal a clear diversity. Including the existence of a phased activity or a connection to a particular event - for example, in the case of single-gender institutions - and the similarity of heterosexual activity - such as marriage between two homosexuals - and those who have bilateral sexual practices ,customary and unknown attitudes. It may be useful to distinguish between homosexual behavior as well as homosexual feelings and homosexual identity that may or may not be identical. Estimates of the spread of the phenomenon are extremely difficult to make, owing to the stigmatization and the socially unapparent nature of the phenomenon. The studies conducted by Kenzi in the United States of America have provided a seven-point scale ranging from absolute homosexuality to full-fledged heterosexuality. Although studies on the causes of homosexuality are extensive, they are not comprehensive and have no indication outside the context of explaining the reasons for sexual trends in general. Much of the attention of sociology has focused instead on the nature of homosexuality, and whether an essentially internal nature - specific to the individual's nature - which is formed through structural social conditions (Marshall, 2000), in other words, is homosexuality and the relationship with the other gender due to social causes ,or are its causes purely biological?

Does the absence of identity threaten social security?, and identity means a community-based unifying or self-conscious identity, and it is not the search for a fixed identity but the need to focus on standardization (Smith, 1998).

The Third Axis: Sociological approaches to the phenomenon of the Boyat:

The sociology of Boyat phenomenon can be studied in gender studies as defined by the World Health Organization as "a central aspect of the human being that includes the biological characteristics that are characteristic of men and women; that is . sexual identity, gender identity, sexual intercourse and reproduction, and sexuality is tested or expressed through Fantasies ,desires, beliefs, attitudes, values, activities, practices, roles and relationships .Sexuality is the result of an overlap between biological, psychological, socioeconomic, historical, cultural, ethical, legal and religious" (Al-Dhalmy, 2009).This definition shows that, in order to explain the phenomenon of Boyat, there are several entrances for understanding the origins of sexual differences; the first entry is a biological perspective.The difference in behavior between women and men is seen as a result of biological differences in specific aspects of human biological structure. The second entry is the social upbringing perspective;meaning that , understanding how expected gender roles are learned through active social actors such as family and media. This approach distinguishes between gender ,its biological meaning and social sexuality.The infant is born with the first element, but learning the second. By communicating with the active factors in the upbringing process, both primary and secondary, children are gradually taught the standards and expectations that match their gender, whether male or female. Sexual differences are not defined by biology but are culturally produced. In contrast, there are those who reject this functional interpretation for two reasons; first, because influential institutions or active factors such as family, schools, and peers may conflict with each other, second, this interpretation ignores the ability of individuals to refuse to comply with social expectations related to gender roles and may move more freely in the field of sexuality.

Individuals are active agents who make and modify roles for themselves. The third entry is the social construction perspective; rather than viewing gender as a biological product and sexuality as a cultural gain, we should consider both gender and sexuality as socially constructed or conceived outcomes that are susceptible to formation and adjustment in various ways. Sexual identities stem from a recognition of gender differences in society and shape them, and when normal people hold fundamentally different cultural values than the majority of society believes, they are characterized by a deviant subculture (Giddens 2001).According to Giddens, the deviant behavior –Boyat in this study - can be seen as a reconstructed or socially conceived outcome, meaning that, every act or practice is formed within a specific social structure that has been subjected to different societal conditions. The individual and the set of characteristics that define his or her identity and nature are determined

by the cultural frameworks prevailing in society, where individual profiling and procreation integrate the fundamental values and trends in the prevailing culture through the process of socialization. There is no doubt that the prevailing values and the established controls of behavior reflect the culture of society and their heritage, while exposing the contradictions and imbalances that have affected the appearance and the integration of the negativeness into the individual's personality in society (Bayoumi, 2001). Understanding and studying the phenomenon needs to be informed of the structural context of society in a specific historical period. In this regard, it is clear that capitalism control and mechanisms are dominant and that concepts such as the concept of "emotional individualism", which means that the roots of the capitalist system and its continuation, have been linked psychologically - strongly - to the suppression of sexual behavior. According to this view, sexual freedom is the key to achieving complete freedom from the routine nature of work and daily life under the capitalist system. The phenomenon can also be understood by addressing the term sexuality and its related concepts, which illustrate the stages of identity and gender terminology that differ historically, from one culture to another, from one environment to another. When they approach gender critically, sociologists test the supposed nature of the link between sex, gender, and the instinct tendency to the other gender (Heterosexuality). Showing that our sexuality is considered social as the rest of our existence, some people, whether male or female, believe that they were born with socially wrong beliefs, and if they were of the other gender, that would change the social outlook of them (Giddens, 2001). The late nineteenth century saw the development of classifications for gender individuals, one can be a homosexual. John Gagnon and William Simon were the first to complete sociological approach to gender; no act or experience could be said to be sexual in itself: It was a matter of social definition. The sociological writings about gender were strongly influenced by feminists and homosexuals after the liberation movement (of Fogambli) in the late 1960s and early 1970s, and the 1990s, with the post-structural impact, saw the formation of a new form of theorizing known as the theory of sexual difference (queer theory) (Scott, 2009), which was used by some theorists as a tool to study the anxiety of all forms of sexual orientation, to break the bilateral encounter between the tendency of the other sex and the tendency of the same sex, to break down all concepts based on the fundamental difference between men and women with regard to gender and sexual identity and to replace them with a cultural and social negotiation (Gamble, 2000); While the vast majority of people in all societies are heterosexual, homosexuality is present in all cultures, although they represent minorities and segments of human beings whose tastes and sexual preferences differ from the dominant pattern. They are those who have sex with people of their own gender, and the practice of homosexuality between women is referred to as "lesbian", while male practice is referred to as "gay" (Marshall, 2000). There are at least ten sexual identities - in addition to lesbians and gays - there are straight women, straight men, hermaphrodite, Bi-sexual men, Bi-sexual women, cross-dressers in women, cross-dressers in men, transgender in men, transgender in women. Criteria for accepting, disregarding, and condemning some of these sexual practices in all human societies arise (Giddens, 2001).

Social control of the environment arises, and progress can be made against this form of deviation by focusing on the victim rather than being limited to a violation of the law (Recio, 2000). Feminism also presented a theoretical framework which is used in this study. The theory of homosexuality in women was active in the framework of the second wave of "radicalism", as an element in the feminist struggle against the "sexual role system", and the controversy between imprinting a sick label of these women and the fact that it is a synonym for the liberation of women and a solution to the problems of sexual relations with men, such as breaking the taboo, rejecting the coercive way of life, as a form of rejection of patriarchal society and resistance behavior, direct or indirect attack on the male's right to reach women, and proceeding from the treatment of the concept of women as the last form of culture by (Simon de Beauvoir) (Gamble, 2000); The way forward is to focus on self-transformation, which raises a central question: Are Boyat based on the desire to seize the self-category, refusing that a man make them to be another, an object ?

There are a number of manifestations of homosexuality in children, most of which fall under the classification of the so-called cross gender behavior, which are signs of a disturbance of the child's sexual identity. These are: 1—Repeated declaration by the child of the desire to belong to the other gender. 2-The constant and strong preference for the roles of the other gender in terms of role-playing. 3-The extreme desire to play the other gender's favorite games. 4-Strong preference for playing with peers from the other gender rather than the same gender. 5-Boys prefer to dress like girls and girls prefer to wear boys' clothes (Wassfy, 2007). We will focus on the latter because it concerns the phenomenon in question, where it is the most widespread stage; that is, the frequent wearing of cross-dressing, a behavior that shows the individual actions within the framework of cultural patterns (Gamble, 2000).

Transvestitism was mentioned in the Encyclopedia of Sociology (Marshall, 2000). The term derived from "Trans" which means transient or opposite, the German word vestines which means clothing. It was drafted by Hirschfeld in 1910. The term Enosim could be used to perform the same meaning (Benjamin, 1967). It is intended for the individual's desire to wear the other gender clothing and play its part. The term is related to transgender, which means the idea of a gender moving from male to female or vice versa, as well as life beyond gender, either temporarily or permanently. Based on a number of cases, it has been found to include four

patterns: Migration pattern resulting in sex substituting, swing pattern or oscillation pattern, is characterized by hidden or veal, erasing pattern, which involves implying, transcending pattern and resulting in the return of gender to originality (redefining) (Ekins and King, 2001).

The causes of sexual delinquency are seen as being rooted in factors that shape individual preparedness, and others that help stabilize the trend, that is, biological and social factors. Biological factors are the increase in the opposite-gender hormone in embryos, the increase in uterine fluids, which increases the babies willingness for the same-gender; if this is met by social factors that have been confirmed ;for example, the same-gender parent, with whom the child has not had a good relationship, the child represents the same-gender behavior and personality of the parent; for example, if the girl finds the mother to be humiliated and disaffected, the girl adapts the father or brother's character to take her right, defends herself, and tends to the male clothing and behavior in defense of her entity. If a boy who is pretty finds female pampering , that is; the mother prefers to see him as a girl, dresses him as a girl, and pampers her male child like a female child, or as if he were a female, sticking to this behavior, and finding his mental comfort (Wassfy, 2007).

This phenomenon was addressed only in a number of limited studies, including (Hefelock , 1936 studies), as well as a limited number of studies, the majority of which are associated with pathological psychology and focus on the phenomenon in males, and there is a lack of counter-treatment of the phenomenon ;that is, in females, Summel even provided a view that, until then, there was no evidence of genes, health, biological or chemical causes to explain this phenomenon, and his view differed from the prevailing thinking then that emphasized biological factors. In fact, the factors of the phenomenon in males were: the unconscious mother's desire to feminize her son, in which case the father is involved in conspiracy by his silence and passiveness toward the subject or for his continued absence (Bullough, 1974). From the foregoing, we conclude that sociological approaches to the phenomenon of Boyat must be addressed at several levels: institutional level: Social frameworks for sexual action such as family and marriage, and ideological level: the control systems and standards that each society has set between normal, perversion, beneficial, harmful, and at the symbolic-cultural level: cultural acts that constitute the social status of the biological community through socialization.

Conclusion:

Although the phenomenon of Boyat can be monitored, by observing their appearance and behavior within the corridors of schools, colleges, institutions and bodies. However, the sensitivity of the subject and the nature of Arab customs and traditions, as well as the lack of previous studies and statistical documentation of their numbers in the Arab societies, which can be relied upon, made it extremely difficult to make estimates of the extent of the spread of the phenomenon because of its stigmatization and the social nature. There were nothing more than lectures, newspaper articles, awareness campaigns, and television symposia.

Successive social changes in our contemporary world have led to radical shifts in the structure of societies that have emerged in behavioral patterns of classes and groups of society, accompanied by alternative ideas, concepts, values and practices that increase our sense of danger. The problem of Boyat is one of those practices that have recently spread and are increasing to the extent that it may seem difficult to control; at the same time, the sensitivity of the problem cannot be overlooked, and discussion of it needs to be understood. We are not calling for pornography, but for a phenomenon that has been known since the beginning of creation (Alkhelyawy). The spread of these insidious behaviors among our customs and traditions has destroyed social security and identity, requiring urgent action to involve all actors in society – government, citizens, the private sector, and civil society – in the face of the phenomenon. In other words, all actors and entities in society should join forces to fight and prevent this phenomenon, and to make people aware of its causes and dangers and how to protect our societies from this scourge. The burden also falls on researchers to study this phenomenon and other immoral phenomena to study in depth socio-anthropology to understand the phenomenon with a view of diagnosing the social and cultural factors surrounding deviant sexual practices and their dimensions on the individual, the family and society as a whole, as well as treatment methods. By employing all these factors in developing appropriate educational and information programs that induce the avoiding of such deviant behaviors, that society at this stage is open to itself, recognizes the problem, and then debate it with an audible voice.

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